

DELIVERABLE D2.2 Due date August 31, 2019.

WP2

Authors: beneficiary Universität Konstanz, Germany, Danilo Nikolic, Wolfgang Belzig

Call: H2020-MSCA-ITN-2017

Type of Action: MSCA-ITN-ETN

Acronym: QuESTech

Number: 766025

Content: Predictions of quantum pumping parameters

Short description

Motivated by the experiments on quantum tunneling in \aleph IS junctions (where \aleph denotes a normal metal proximitized by a superconductor) performed by ESR 4 Bayan Karimi and professor Jukka Pekola from ALLTO University, we were supposed to make a theoretical model which can explain the novel behavior of the conductance for the zero-bias voltage. Namely, it turns out that the height of the zero-bias peak in conductance scales linearly with the temperature which makes the system appropriate for measuring the low temperatures.

Our work consists of two parts

- Description of the proximitized normal metal \aleph in the framework of the quasiclassical Green's function formalism in the dirty limit described by the Usadel equation of motion.
- Analysis of the single electron tunneling in a \aleph IS system, where we employ so called $P(E)$ theory.

Proximitized normal metal

In order to describe the properties of the proximitized normal metal \aleph , we consider different geometries of SN contacts (see Fig. 1) treated in the framework of Quasiclassical Green's functions in the dirty limit which are solutions of the Usadel equation

$$\frac{D}{2} \frac{\partial^2 \theta(E, y)}{\partial y^2} = (-iE + \Gamma_{in}) \sin[\theta(E, y)] - \Delta(y) \cos[\theta(E, y)],$$

where D is the diffusion constant which characterizes the material, θ is so called proximity angle, E is the energy of quasiparticle excitations, Γ_{in} is the energy due to inelastic scattering processes, $\Delta(y)$ is the superconducting gap.

Fig. 1. A SNIS junction of (a) a wire and (b) an overlap geometry

Once known proximity angle θ allows us to obtain all the spectral properties of \aleph .

Single particle tunneling in a \aleph IS

We are supposed to analyze the quantum tunneling in a \aleph IS junction of different geometries (the tunnel contact of a resistance R_T , see Fig. 1). In the experimental realization the junction is coupled to an electromagnetic environment which influences the tunneling processes through the barrier. The

probability of emission of a photon of energy E into an electromagnetic environment which the junction is coupled to during the tunneling process is given by the so-called $P(E)$ function, which depends on the configuration of the environment. If we deal with a Josephson tunnel junction, the quantum transport is mediated by the Cooper pairs and the current is directly proportional to the $P(E)$

$$I_s(V) = \frac{\pi e E_J^2}{\hbar} (P(2eV) - P(-2eV)),$$

where E_J is the Josephson energy and V is a bias voltage applied to the system.

RC transmission line

We consider a junction coupled to an electromagnetic environment (see Fig. 2) modelled as an infinite RC line with the corresponding impedance

$$Z(\omega) = \sqrt{\frac{R}{i\omega C_0}},$$

where R and C_0 are resistance and capacitance per unit length of the line, respectively.

Fig. 2 Schema of the system under study.

Fig. 3 (a) shows the IV characteristics of an overlap NIS system (see Fig.1 (b)) coupled to an infinite RC transmission line for various temperatures and experimentally relevant selection of parameters. The zero-bias conductance (solid lines) with the direct comparison to the experiment (bubble) is given in Fig. 3 (b). We can observe a good agreement with the experiment.

In this report we have given a short overview on our progress in modelling of an ultra-sensitive thermometer based on the Cooper pair tunneling processes, which was experimentally proposed by ESR 4 Bayan Karimi and Professor Jukka Pekola. In order to make a link to the energy pumping processes (calorimetry) we can recall relation between the heat (ΔQ) and the temperature increment (ΔT) given by the simple expression

$$\Delta Q = C_v \Delta T,$$

where C_v the heat capacity at constant volume.

Fig. 3. Panel (a): The I - V characteristics in the system for different temperatures. Panel (b): Comparison between the theory (solid lines) and the experiment (circles) for the zero-bias conductance as a function of temperature in a NIS system. In the theory the junction is coupled to an infinite RC transmission line of the unit capacitance equal to the capacitance of the junction and the unit resistance $R = 0.3K\Omega$ (see Fig. 2). Other parameters related to the junction are taken like in the experiment.